

DIMENSION PREDICTION AND CONTROL FOR RTM PROCESSES

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ABSTRACT: With the increasing demand for composite products to be affordable, net-shaped and efficiently assembled, tight dimension tolerance is critical. Due to lack of accurate process models, dimension analysis and control for resin transfer molding (RTM) processes are often performed using trial-and-error approaches based on engineers' experiences or previous production data. Such approaches are limited to specific geometry and materials and often fail to achieve the required dimensional accuracy in the final products. This paper presents a dimension prediction and compensation approach based on a dimension variation model, which is built based on process simulation, the classical laminate theory (CLT) and finite element analysis (FEA) method. The approach provides a tool to predict and control dimension variations in RTM processes. The model was validated against experimental data. Using this model, deformations of common features in typical composite structures were analyzed. Design parameters were identified and related to dimension deformation. The structural tree method is presented for tolerance analysis and synthesis of assemblies of composites.

KEY WORDS: Resin Transfer Molding, Finite Element Analysis, Dimension Control, Composite Assembly

INTRODUCTION

The applications of advanced composites are important in both commercial and military products due to their structural and functional features. With the increasing demand for composite products to be affordable, net-shaped and efficiently assembled, tight dimension tolerances are often required. However, the conventional methodologies of controlling warpage and dimension control for composites are mainly based on thermal residual stress analysis using simple geometry. These methods cannot be effectively employed in real world part design and tooling development. This is largely due to the lack of accurate process models. As a result, the trial-and-error method is still dominating dimension control operations in composite manufacturing and assembly. In another aspect, the new applications of processes, such as RTM and resin infusion, will also raise a number of new issues in dimension control. For example, large warpage is observed due to the occurrences of resin rich surfaces and resin rich pocket phenomena during the processes.

The problem of dimension deformation for composite parts comes from the volumetric shrinkage of the resin during curing and the mismatch in the coefficients of thermal expansion of the matrix and the fiber. Deformation of composites due to thermal stress can be classified as process-induced and structure-induced. Primary causes include crosslinking, non-uniform thermal expansion, shrinkage and residual stresses induced in the curing and cooling processes.

Until recently did deformation of composites receive researchers' attention. Spring-in is a common problem in composite fabrication caused by the difference between the in-plane thermal expansion coefficient and the through-thickness thermal expansion coefficient.

For simple geometric structures as “L-shaped,” the spring-in has been analytically computed for autoclave process [1-5], RTM process [1-4] and filament winding process [6-8].

In order to predict the spring-in of more complex structures, numerical simulation tools of finite element method or finite difference method have been employed. Theriault *et al* [9] developed a one-dimensional finite difference model to simulate the progression of material properties during the processing of metal-clad, multi-layered, fiber mat reinforced, thermoset resins. The general Classical Lamination Theory was implemented to evaluate the dimensional movement of the composite laminate. The spring-in was predicted using FEM by Wiersma *et al* [10]. His approach includes curing simulation, elastic model and viscoelastic model. Darrow and Smith [11-12] employed finite element method to model the processing induced spring-in in laminated composites. Their model accounted for the mold stretching, thickness shrinkage, and fiber volume fraction gradients. This linear elastic model was able to account for 80% of the observed spring-in for parts ranging between 1 and 5 mm thick and having a 3 to 13 mm bend radius. Golestanian and El-Gizawy [13] modeled the process-induced residual stresses and deformation in composite parts using finite element method coupled with cure-dependent mechanical properties. Wang *et al* [14] conducted finite element analysis of spring-in using ABAQUS.

Figure 1: Model construction and validation

The literature survey indicates that most research is focused on simple geometry deformation prediction in composite manufacturing. In addition, few studies have addressed the issue of deformation and tolerances of composite assembly. The measurement and assessment of deformation in composite manufacturing require thorough study.

With the rapid advancement of computing techniques, composite process simulation has become a powerful tool in industry. The ultimate goal of this research is to develop a methodology and engineering tools for fabricating high quality composite components through dimensional prediction and control at the design stage. This composite dimension control study integrates such functional components as thermal stress analysis, dimensional deformation prediction and compensation, and mold modification.

DIMENSION VARIATION MODEL

For the purpose of deformation prediction for the RTM process, a dimension variation model [14-15] was developed and validated. The approach is illustrated in Figure 1. A non-isothermal flow and curing model was developed to simulate the flow pattern and temperature distribution. A material model was used to compute the material properties, i.e. CTE, moduli, etc. These results, with the design geometry and processing parameters, were imported into the dimension variation model, which was based on the CLT and FEA, to compute the deformation. Using the same design geometry, material properties and processing parameters, experimental parts were fabricated and measured using a coordinate measuring machine for the purpose of validation. The measured data and the computational results were compared and the model parameters were revised to provide as accurate prediction as possible. The validated model was used for deformation and tolerance analysis of typical structures and deformation compensation.

Figure 2: A single-stiffener structure

Figure 3: Mold assembly for single-stiffener structure

A single-stiffener, as shown in Figure 2, was modeled using the developed dimension variation model. Experiments were conducted for validation. The mold assembly is shown in Figure 3. A cross ply E-

glass/epoxy laminate of $[0/90]_s$, was studied. First, the fiber volume fraction was determined. Before the experiment, the fiber mats was weighed using a scale and its mass is 36.8g; after the part was fabricated, as shown in Figure 4, the final part was weighed and its mass is 101.11g. The fiber volume fraction is 22%. This data was used in the material model.

Figure 4: Finished single stiffener structure part

Figure 5: Resin rich zones

After the thickness was determined, the single stiffener structure was modeled. Due to the lay-up of fiber mats, resin rich zones are formed, as shown in Figure 5, which should be accounted for in modeling. The finite element mesh was shown in Figure 6(a). Half of the structure was modeled and the symmetric boundary condition was applied. The computational result is shown in Figure 6(b), where the contour indicates the total displacement in mm. The spring-in angle is -0.49° .

(a): Mesh

(b): Spring-in of $[0/90]_s$ laminate

Figure 6: FEA of single stiffener structure

The spring-in angle was measured 10 times on the CMM. The measurement data was shown in Table 1. The average of the spring-in angle is -0.52° .

In the same approach, a unidirectional E-glass/epoxy laminate of $[90]_4$ was studied. The computational result is -0.044° . The spring-in was measured 25 times using the CMM. After deleting the outlier, the spring-in is -0.080° . The results of both parts show that the measured spring-in is larger than the computational one. The error is due to the resin rich zones that were not included in the model and measuring uncertainty.

Table 1: Spring-in measurement of single-stiffener

n	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	Avg.
spring-in (°)	-0.506	-0.466	-0.616	-0.595	-0.469	-0.436	-0.493	-0.481	-0.516	-0.632	-0.521

TYPICAL COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

The ultimate purpose of this research is reducing dimension variation and achieving better dimension control. A complex composite component can often be regarded as the combination of several typical geometric features such as L-shaped structures, cylindrical shells, etc. Therefore, research attention can be focused onto these typical structures to achieve a common guideline for composite structural design.

The deformation of composites is related with design geometric parameters, material parameters and processing parameters. This gives us a functional relationship as

$$\delta = f(G, M, P) \quad (1)$$

where,

δ : deformation vector;

G : design geometric parameters;

M : material parameters (fiber, resin);

P : processing parameters (curing temperature, etc.).

First, the geometric parameters were studied. Four most used typical structures, their corresponding tolerances, and design parameters are summarized in Table 2. In order to isolate the effects of geometric parameters from the influences of materials and processing, the materials were chosen to be E-glass and epoxy. Regression models were developed for these four typical E-glass/epoxy structures.

After the regression models for E-glass/epoxy laminates were developed, they were expanded to other fiber/matrix systems. When other fiber/matrix system is used, these regression models need to be revised. Based on semi-empirical analysis, a correction coefficient C is introduced. The final regression models for any fiber/matrix system are summarized in Table 3. The correction coefficients for some fiber/matrix systems are shown in Table 4.

Table 2: Typical structures and design parameters

Typical structures	 Cylindrical shell			
Tolerances	Perpendicularity Angularity	Perpendicularity	Perpendicularity Parallelism	Cylindricity
Design parameters	Angle ϕ Radius r Thickness h	Thickness h Radius r	Thickness h Radius r	Radius r Thickness h

Table 3: Regression models for typical composite structures

L-shaped structure	$\Delta\phi = C(-0.826 + 0.951V_f)$
Single-stiffener structure	$\Delta\phi = C\left[-0.073 - \left(0.003 + 0.040e^{-\frac{h}{1.264}}\right)r + 0.173(V_f - 0.49)\right]$
Double-stiffener structure	$\Delta\phi_v = C\left[0.066 + 0.3e^{-\frac{h}{0.971}} + \left(0.016 + 0.121e^{-\frac{h}{1.207}}\right)r - 0.561(V_f - 0.49)\right]$
Half cylindrical shell	$T_{cy} = C[0.012(1 - V_f)r]$

Table 4: Correction coefficients for typical composite structures

Fiber/matrix system	Correction coefficient	
	L-shaped structures and cylindrical shells	Stiffener structures
E-glass/epoxy	1.00	1.00
Carbon/epoxy	1.37	1.00
E-glass/polyester	2.12	2.12
Carbon/polyester	2.80	2.12

STRUCTURAL TREE METHOD

After the deformation and tolerances of typical structures are studied and the regression models are obtained, they can be used for assembly tolerance analysis and synthesis. In this study, a structural tree method based on structural analysis and coordinate transformation was developed for composite assembly tolerance analysis and synthesis. The advantage of the structural tree method is that it uses simple regression models instead of finite element analysis to perform the dimension prediction. Therefore, the amount of computational efforts is greatly reduced. The procedure of the structural tree method is as follows.

1. For given composite assemblies, from the origin, identify typical structures, e.g. L-shaped structures, single-stiffener structures.
2. Assign deformation feature points $\mathbf{N}_1 \dots \mathbf{N}_n$ based on typical structure study. In general, these points locate at the curved part of these structures.
3. Construct the structural tree based on these points; each point will form a node of the tree.

$$\textcircled{\mathbf{N}_0} \longrightarrow \textcircled{\mathbf{N}_1} \longrightarrow \dots \longrightarrow \textcircled{\mathbf{N}_n}$$

4. Using the regression models, determine the rotational angle ε_i of node i with reference to its prior node along the path; Formulate the conversion matrix $\mathbf{R}_{\mathbf{N}_i\mathbf{N}_{i-1}}$ as

$$\mathbf{R}_{\mathbf{N}_i\mathbf{N}_{i-1}} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \varepsilon_i & -\sin \varepsilon_i \\ \sin \varepsilon_i & \cos \varepsilon_i \end{bmatrix}. \quad (2)$$

5. Formulate deformation relations for node \mathbf{N}_i as

$$\delta_{\mathbf{N}_i} = \delta_{\mathbf{N}_{i-1}} + \left[\prod_{j=1}^i \mathbf{R}_{\mathbf{N}_j\mathbf{N}_{j-1}} \right] (\mathbf{N}_i - \mathbf{N}_{i-1}) - (\mathbf{N}_i - \mathbf{N}_{i-1}) \quad (3)$$

i.e.,

$$\delta_{N_i} = \left\{ \sum_{j=1}^i \left[\prod_{k=1}^j \mathbf{R}_{N_k, N_{k-1}} \right] (\mathbf{N}_j - \mathbf{N}_{j-1}) \right\} - (\mathbf{N}_i - \mathbf{N}_0). \quad (4)$$

- After the deformation and tolerances of all nodes are obtained, find the total deformation and tolerance of assembly.

Figure 7: A triangle assembly structure

A more complex assembly composed of two single-stiffener structures and an L-shaped structure, as shown in Figure 7, was studied. The structural tree for this example is constructed as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Structural tree for the assembly shown in Figure 7

The deformation relations for each branch are shown as follows, respectively. For simplification, all the spring-in angles take positive values. According to the structural tree method, the rotational matrices and the displacement at C can be formulated as:

$$\mathbf{R}_{AO} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \varepsilon_1 & \sin \varepsilon_1 \\ -\sin \varepsilon_1 & \cos \varepsilon_1 \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{R}_{BA} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos 2\varepsilon_2 & \sin 2\varepsilon_2 \\ -\sin 2\varepsilon_2 & \cos 2\varepsilon_2 \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{R}_{CB} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \varepsilon_3 & -\sin \varepsilon_3 \\ \sin \varepsilon_3 & \cos \varepsilon_3 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \delta_C &= \mathbf{R}_{AO}(\mathbf{A} - \mathbf{O}) + \mathbf{R}_{BA} \mathbf{R}_{AO}(\mathbf{B} - \mathbf{A}) + \mathbf{R}_{CB} \mathbf{R}_{BA} \mathbf{R}_{AO}(\mathbf{C} - \mathbf{B}) - \mathbf{C} \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} -1500 \cos \varepsilon_1 - 500 \cos(\varepsilon_1 + 2\varepsilon_2) - 100 \sin(\varepsilon_1 + 2\varepsilon_2 - \varepsilon_3) + 2000 \\ 1500 \sin \varepsilon_1 + 500 \sin(\varepsilon_1 + 2\varepsilon_2) - 100 \cos(\varepsilon_1 + 2\varepsilon_2 - \varepsilon_3) + 100 \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

In order to formulate the displacement at F, α needs to be calculated first with the following procedure:

$$\mathbf{R}_{DA} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \varepsilon_2 & \sin \varepsilon_2 \\ -\sin \varepsilon_2 & \cos \varepsilon_2 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{D}' &= \mathbf{R}_{AO}(\mathbf{A} - \mathbf{O}) + \mathbf{R}_{DA} \mathbf{R}_{AO}(\mathbf{D} - \mathbf{A}) \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} -1500 \cos \varepsilon_1 + 500 \sin(\varepsilon_1 + \varepsilon_2) \\ 1500 \sin \varepsilon_1 + 500 \cos(\varepsilon_1 + \varepsilon_2) \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

$$\alpha = \tan^{-1}[(y_P - y_D)/(x_P - x_D)] - \tan^{-1}[(y_P - y_D')/(x_P - x_D')]$$

The displacement at **C** can be formulated as

$$\mathbf{R}_{EP} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \alpha & \sin \alpha \\ -\sin \alpha & \cos \alpha \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{R}_{FE} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \varepsilon_4 & -\sin \varepsilon_4 \\ \sin \varepsilon_4 & \cos \varepsilon_4 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \delta_F &= \mathbf{R}_{EP}(\mathbf{E} - \mathbf{P}) + \mathbf{R}_{FE}\mathbf{R}_{EP}(\mathbf{F} - \mathbf{E}) - (\mathbf{F} - \mathbf{P}) \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} -2500\cos \alpha - 833\sin \alpha - 267\sin(\alpha - \varepsilon_4) + 2500 \\ 2500\sin \alpha - 833\cos \alpha - 267\cos(\alpha - \varepsilon_4) + 1100 \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

The assembly deformation between point **F** and point **C** can be found as

$$\delta_T = \delta_C - \delta_F$$

When $r = 6.35\text{mm}$, $h = 3.175\text{mm}$, the spring-in angles were computed using the non-linear regression models. The deformation was computed as $\delta_C = [0.05 \ 5.90]^T$ and $\delta_F = [-0.18 \ 3.44]^T$. Thus, $\delta_T = [0.23 \ 2.46]^T$ and $\|\delta_T\|_2 = 2.47$.

When the design parameters are bounded, the assembly deformation can be minimized using non-linear optimization techniques. Sequential quadratic method was used in this study. The objective function and constraints are listed below:

$$\text{Min } \|\delta_T\|_2$$

Subject to:

$$3 \leq r_1 \leq 12; \quad 3 \leq r_2 \leq 12; \quad 3 \leq r_3 \leq 12;$$

$$3 \leq h_1 \leq 3.25; \quad h_1 = h_2 = h_3$$

$$0.45 \leq V_{f1} \leq 0.55; \quad 0.45 \leq V_{f2} \leq 0.55; \quad 0.45 \leq V_{f3} \leq 0.55.$$

After optimization, the assembly deformation is $\|\delta_T\|_2 = 1.76$, as show in Table 5.

Table 5: Assembly deformation optimization

	Before optimization	After optimization
r_1 (mm)	6.35	6.37
h_1 (mm)	3.175	3.25
V_{f1}	0.49	0.55
r_2 (mm)	6.35	3.00
h_2 (mm)	3.175	3.25
V_{f2}	0.49	0.55
r_3 (mm)	6.35	6.35
h_3 (mm)	3.175	3.25
V_{f3}	0.49	0.45
Assembly deformation (mm)	2.47	1.76

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, a dimension variation model based on the classical laminate theory and finite element analysis provides an effective tool to predict dimension variations in resin transfer molding processes. Case studies show that this model can satisfactorily predict deformations. Deformation and tolerances of typical structures were computed using this model. Design parameters were identified and related to dimension deformation and tolerances. The structural tree method is presented for tolerance analysis and synthesis of composite assemblies.

Compared with previous studies on composite dimension variations and control, the advantages of this approach are the ability to:

1. Handle complex geometry and assemblies;
2. Provide designers with guidelines for typical composite structure designs; and
3. Compensate for deformation to allow for effective dimension control at the early design stage.

As indicated earlier, errors of certain level for dimension prediction for parts with complex geometry still occur. The errors are believed to be caused by the negligence of some processing factors, such as resin rich areas. The future work for this study will include such factors in the model and should improve dimension accuracy.

REFERENCES

1. Jain, L.K. and Mai, Y.W., "On Residual Stress Induced Distortions during Fabrication of Composite Shells," *Proceedings of the 1995 10th Technical Conference of the American Society for Composites*, 261-270 (1995)
2. Jain, L.K. and Mai, Y.W., "On Residual Stress Induced Distortions during Fabrication of Composite Shells," *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites*, 15(8): 793-805 (1996)
3. Jain, L.K. and Mai, Y.W., "Stresses and Deformations Induced during Manufacturing. Part I: Theoretical Analysis of Composite Cylinders and Shells," *Journal of Composite Materials*, 31(7) 673-695 (1997)
4. Jain, L.K., Lutton, B.G., Mai, Y.W. and Paton, R., "Stresses and Deformations Induced during Manufacturing. Part II: A Study of the Spring-in Phenomenon," *Journal of Composite Materials*, 31(7) 696-719 (1997)
5. Huang, C.K. and Yang, S.Y., "Warping in Advanced Composite Tools with Varying Angles and Radii," *Composites Part A*, 28A(9-10): 891-893 (1997)
6. Meink, T. and Shen, M.H.H., "Processing Induced Warpage in Composite Cylindrical Shells Part I," *12th Engineering Mechanics Conference* (1998)
7. Meink, T. and Shen, M.H.H., "Processing Induced Warpage in Composite Cylindrical Shells Part I," *ASME Winter Annual Meeting* (1998)
8. Meink, T. and Shen, M.H.H., "Processing Induced Warpage in Composite Cylindrical Shells," in *Advances in composite materials and mechanics*, ed. by Arup Maji, American Society of Civil Engineers, Reston, VA, 1-12 (1999)
9. Theriault, R. P. and Osswald, T. A., "Processing Induced Residual Stress in Asymmetric Laminate Panels," *Polymer Composites*, 20(3): 493-509 (1999)
10. Wiersma, H.W., Peeters, L.J.B. and Akkerman, R., "Prediction of Springforward in Continuous-Fiber/Polymer L-Shaped Parts," *Composites Part A*, 29A(11): 1333-1342 (1998)
11. Darrow, D.A., Jr. and Smith, L.V., "Evaluating the Spring-in Phenomenon of Polymer Matrix Composites," *33rd International SAMPE Technical Conference*, 33: 326-337 (2001)
12. Darrow, D.A., Jr. and Smith, L.V., "Isolating Components of Processing Induced Warpage in Laminated Composites," *Journal of Composite Materials*, 36(21): 2407-2419 (2002)

13. Golestanian, H. and El-Gizawy, A.S., "Modeling of Process Induced Residual Stresses in Resin Transfer Molded Composites with Woven Fiber Mats," *Journal of Composite Materials*, 35(1): 1513-1528 (2001)
14. Wang, J., Kelly, D. and Hillier, W., "Finite Element Analysis of Temperature Induced Stresses and Deformations of Polymer Composite Components," *Journal of Composite Materials*, 34(17): 1456-1471 (2000)
15. Dong, C.S., Zhang C., Liang, Z.Y., and Wang, B., "Dimension Prediction and Control for Composite Assembly," *Proceedings of SAMPE 2003 (48th ISSE)*, Long Beach, CA (2003)
16. Dong, C.S., Zhang C., Liang, Z.Y., and Wang, B., "Dimension Prediction and Control for Resin Transfer Molding Process," *Proceedings of the Fourth International Conference on Composite Science and Technology (ICCST/4)*, Durban, South Africa (2003)
17. Dong, C.S., Zhang C., Liang, Z.Y., and Wang, B., "Dimension Prediction and Control for Resin Transfer Molding Process," submitted to *Composites, Part A*